

THE AUTHORITARIAN MOMENT OF THE LIBERAL ARTS

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Introduction

The Liberal Arts have long been considered a pillar of intellectual freedom, fostering creativity, critical thinking, and a broad understanding of the human condition. Yet, in recent years, these institutions have undergone a shift toward what can be described as an “*authoritarian moment*.” Once spaces for diverse and challenging ideas, they now often impose ideological conformity, demand compulsory participation, and operate within increasingly commercialized frameworks. Drawing on the works of philosophers such as Michel Foucault, Gilles Deleuze, and Giorgio Agamben, this essay will explore how Liberal Arts education has transitioned from a liberating force to a mechanism of control. It will examine the pressures to conform, the instrumentalization of safe spaces, the role of surveillance, and the economic commodification of education.

1. The Disciplinary Society versus Control Society

Foucault’s concept of the *disciplinary society*, with its rigid institutional boundaries and surveillance practices, laid the groundwork for understanding modern systems of control. In a disciplinary society, individuals were confined within spaces like schools, prisons, or hospitals, where their behavior was strictly regulated. Liberal Arts institutions originally aimed to break from these rigid structures, encouraging critical thought and independence. However, in the current era, we see a shift toward what Gilles Deleuze described as the *control society*, where power is exerted not through confinement but through continuous monitoring and subtle mechanisms of control.

In the context of Liberal Arts, control is exercised digitally. The transition to online learning, especially accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, has intensified this shift. Students are no longer simply attending lectures; they are expected to be visible at all times via platforms like Zoom, with their cameras and microphones on, a practice that resonates with Foucault’s *panopticism*. The panoptic effect—where individuals modify their behavior because they feel they are constantly being watched—has become digitalized. The university, instead of a space for intellectual exploration, becomes a virtual panopticon where students are both participants and subjects of surveillance.

2. The Coercion of Participation: The New Form of Discipline

In traditional disciplinary societies, students could opt for passive participation or even silence without facing severe repercussions. However, in today’s Liberal Arts institutions, there is a paradox: the once-liberating environment now imposes participation as a compulsory act. Deleuze’s idea of the *control society* is critical here. Rather than being confined within a physical institution, students are subject to a fluid, ongoing demand for engagement. The omnipresence of digital platforms means that

students are not only expected to attend but to actively contribute to discussions and display their engagement.

This shift reflects a broader societal change from punishment by confinement to punishment by exclusion. If a student chooses not to participate, they risk being excluded from the academic and social life of the institution. As Giorgio Agamben argues in his concept of the *homo sacer*, modern power structures often create sacrificial figures, individuals who are excluded from the social order and lose their rights without formal punishment. In the Liberal Arts, this sacrificial figure manifests as the student who refuses to comply with participation norms. If they fail to turn on their camera, speak, or submit assignments on time, they become a pariah—excluded not just from the course but from the collective academic experience. This exclusion operates as a form of symbolic death, severing their connection to the institution and its community.

3. Ideological Conformity: The Weaponization of Liberal Values

One of the most striking developments in the contemporary Liberal Arts is the imposition of ideological conformity under the banner of liberal values. While these institutions claim to champion diversity of thought, in practice, they often enforce a narrow set of political and moral beliefs. In his book *The Authoritarian Moment*, Ben Shapiro argues that institutions originally designed to foster open discourse have weaponized their authority to suppress dissent. This claim resonates in the Liberal Arts, where students and faculty members who challenge the dominant ideology may face social ostracism or even academic penalties.

Foucault's work on the relationship between power and knowledge provides a framework for understanding this dynamic. In the Liberal Arts, power is exercised through the control of discourse. Professors and administrators, who hold the power to shape curriculum, grading, and academic recognition, become arbiters of what constitutes acceptable thought. The selection process for students—especially through motivation letters and interviews—further reflects this dynamic. These processes are not merely about assessing academic ability but serve as tools for ideological filtering. Students are assessed not just on their knowledge but on their perceived moral and political alignment.

This ideological conformity extends to classroom discussions. Controversial topics such as war, gender identity, or international politics are often framed within a specific moral and political context, where deviation from the accepted viewpoint is discouraged. Agamben's concept of the *homo sacer* once again applies here: dissenters become social outcasts, rendered "bare life"—they are stripped of their voice and significance within the institutional framework.

4. Commercialization: The Commodification of Education

A significant factor driving this authoritarian moment is the increasing commercialization of higher education. As universities seek funding from external sources such as grants, foundations, and government agencies, the needs of the student are subordinated to the demands of these financial backers. Foucault's analysis of neoliberalism is relevant here, as institutions become more concerned with maintaining their financial viability than with the educational experience of their students.

In this context, the student is reduced to a transaction—a mere data point in the larger economic framework of the university. The pressure to satisfy external stakeholders shifts the focus of education from intellectual growth to marketable outcomes. Course offerings are often tailored to the perceived interests of donors or aligned with popular political movements to secure funding. This process leads to a form of “edutainment,” where the quality of the educational product is secondary to its appeal to external audiences.

Moreover, the emphasis on student satisfaction—often measured through superficial metrics like student evaluations—compounds this problem. The market-driven nature of the university encourages a transactional relationship between students and faculty, where grades and diplomas are treated as commodities rather than as markers of intellectual achievement. In this system, the student is no longer a learner but a customer, and education becomes a product to be consumed.

5. Safe Spaces: The Paradox of Protection

The rise of “safe spaces” in Liberal Arts institutions is another aspect of this authoritarian moment. Designed to protect students from harm and ensure inclusivity, these spaces often become zones of ideological policing. While the intention may be to foster a supportive environment, in practice, they serve as mechanisms to enforce conformity. Any deviation from the accepted discourse is seen as a threat to the community’s safety, and dissenting voices are swiftly silenced.

Foucault’s analysis of power relations can help us understand the dynamics at play in safe spaces. By creating zones where certain ideas or expressions are deemed unacceptable, institutions establish invisible boundaries around what can and cannot be discussed. This form of control operates not through explicit censorship but through the internalization of norms. Students, aware of the social consequences of dissent, self-censor to avoid exclusion or punishment.

Safe spaces, then, paradoxically limit the very intellectual freedom they are meant to protect. By imposing strict ideological boundaries, they prevent the open exchange of ideas that is central to the Liberal Arts tradition. This dynamic echoes the broader trend of control societies described by Deleuze, where power operates not through confinement but through subtle forms of social coercion.

6. Digital Surveillance and the Internalization of Control

In the current landscape of Liberal Arts institutions, surveillance extends far beyond the traditional panopticism of physical oversight described by Michel Foucault. What we are witnessing now is the internalization of control mechanisms, which Gilles Deleuze predicted in his theory of the *control society*. In this context, surveillance is no longer confined to institutional apparatuses like schools or prisons, where behavior was regulated through confinement. Instead, it operates in fluid and subtle ways, embedding itself into the very fabric of educational life.

With the advent of digital learning platforms like Zoom, the line between public and private life in education has blurred. Cameras and microphones—once optional tools of communication—have become compulsory instruments of surveillance. While students sit in their private spaces, they are nonetheless expected to be perpetually visible, contributing to what Deleuze calls the *modulation* of control. Unlike Foucault’s

model of the panopticon, where individuals are confined within physical boundaries and overseen from a central point, Deleuze's control society operates through continuous, subtle shifts in surveillance that make individuals feel as though they are being observed everywhere and at all times. This dynamic creates a pressure to conform to expected behaviors in both classroom performance and personal expression.

The requirement for constant online visibility mirrors what Foucault describes in *Discipline and Punish* as the power of the gaze. In Foucault's terms, surveillance produces "docile bodies"—individuals who internalize the sense of being watched and thus modify their behavior to fit prescribed norms. In today's Liberal Arts classrooms, students are often judged not just by their intellectual contributions, but also by their willingness to "perform" participation visibly. The assumption is that a lack of visible engagement—reflected in an inactive camera or muted microphone—is a sign of intellectual disengagement or defiance, even though such indicators may have little to do with actual involvement in the course material.

7. Peer Surveillance and Self-Censorship

The most insidious aspect of modern surveillance in Liberal Arts education is how it leads to the internalization of control, where students and faculty become agents of their own policing. This process occurs through peer surveillance, a phenomenon where students monitor and judge each other's behaviors, opinions, and levels of engagement. This dynamic turns the classroom into an environment where students police not just their own behavior but that of their peers, in line with the expectations set by the institution. Deleuze's description of societies of control as operating through *free-floating power* is crucial here; there are no clear boundaries of who is enforcing the rules, as students and faculty alike internalize the gaze and start policing each other.

Foucault's idea of *biopower*—the regulation of bodies and populations—can also be applied here. In Liberal Arts institutions, power is no longer about physical coercion but about the subtle shaping of thought, behavior, and identity. This biopower manifests in students who constantly assess how they should act to avoid being labeled as "non-conforming" or "disengaged." The fear of exclusion or marginalization leads to self-censorship, where students avoid challenging dominant narratives or expressing dissenting views, not because they are physically silenced, but because they have absorbed the belief that certain opinions are unacceptable.

8. The Paranoia of Control: Fear of External and Internal Threats

Surveillance in Liberal Arts institutions is not only an institutional phenomenon but also a social one. The fear of infiltration by external authorities—be they government, corporations, or other power structures—compounds the anxiety that students and faculty experience. Liberal Arts institutions often pride themselves on being bastions of progressive thought and critique, but this self-conception is undermined by the omnipresent paranoia that someone might disrupt the ideological unity of the collective. In such a climate, the fear of "outside threats" often leads to hypervigilance within the academic community itself.

In an atmosphere where everyone is suspected of being a potential "dissenter" or "outsider," individuals adopt the gaze of the "Big Brother"—a figure who embodies

the surveillance and control mechanisms typically associated with state power. This internalization of the surveillance state creates a situation in which liberal students and professors themselves become enforcers of the very control structures they seek to resist. They impose ideological conformity not through direct coercion, but through an atmosphere of paranoia and distrust. Here, Deleuze's insight that in control societies, people regulate themselves even without explicit external pressure, becomes starkly apparent. The surveillance state becomes diffused across the institution, with every member playing a part in maintaining its disciplinary boundaries.

9. Safe Spaces as Zones of Hyper-Surveillance

The creation of “safe spaces,” originally intended to be areas of protection and emotional support, often transforms into zones of heightened surveillance. These spaces are typically presented as environments free from harmful speech and ideologies, but they also function as zones of ideological control. In safe spaces, the boundaries of acceptable discourse are tightly regulated, and any deviation from the dominant narrative is seen as a threat to the collective safety of the group. This turns the safe space into a surveillance mechanism where speech and behavior are closely monitored to ensure conformity with institutional values.

In Foucault's terms, this is a form of *governmentality*—a way of governing individuals by regulating their thoughts and behaviors not through direct coercion but through norms and values that they internalize. In these environments, the pressure to conform is so intense that students often preemptively silence themselves, aware that any deviation from the collective norms could result in exclusion. The irony here is that what is intended to be a refuge from harm often becomes a site of policing and exclusion, mirroring the control dynamics Deleuze described.

10. Internalized Surveillance and the Production of Conformity

The internalization of surveillance ultimately leads to the production of conformity, where individuals regulate their own behavior to avoid the perceived or actual threat of exclusion. This dynamic aligns with Deleuze's argument that in societies of control, individuals are continuously modulated by external expectations. In the case of Liberal Arts institutions, the constant demand for engagement, ideological alignment, and visible participation ensures that students conform not because they are forced to, but because they believe it is the only way to survive within the system. This conformity is not a conscious act of obedience but a subconscious response to the subtle mechanisms of control that permeate the educational environment.

The fear of being excluded or ostracized becomes the driving force behind behavior, creating a culture of compliance and self-surveillance that undermines the very principles of intellectual freedom and diversity that the Liberal Arts claim to uphold. The system, through these mechanisms of surveillance and internal control, produces subjects who are not only compliant but who believe that their compliance is necessary for their continued participation in the academic community.

Conclusion

In conclusion, surveillance in the Liberal Arts has evolved from the physical and institutional oversight described by Foucault to the internalized, fluid, and digital control theorized by Deleuze. This new form of control permeates every aspect of

academic life, from the digital classroom to peer interactions, creating a culture of self-surveillance, conformity, and fear. The Liberal Arts, once seen as spaces of intellectual freedom, have become environments where students and faculty are constantly monitored—by both external technologies and internalized expectations of behavior. This authoritarian moment of the Liberal Arts mirrors the broader societal shift toward control societies, where power is exercised not through explicit coercion but through subtle mechanisms of surveillance and internal regulation.

The recommended bibliographical list includes works by foundational thinkers like Foucault and Deleuze, whose theories of surveillance and control are central to understanding the dynamics at play in contemporary Liberal Arts institutions. Additionally, Agamben's work on sovereignty and exclusion provides insight into the sacrificial dynamics that occur when students are excluded from these systems. Lastly, Shapiro's *The Authoritarian Moment* offers a critique of ideological conformity, while Zuboff's work addresses the broader context of digital surveillance and its implications for society.

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